

INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article will focus on the fact that innovative activity is a complex of educational technologies, as well as on the fact that the main task of this process is to transform the components of the pedagogical process, as well as on the purpose and content of education, means, methods and forms of training, management systems.

The innovation process in education is a set of procedures and means by which a didactic idea is transformed into an educational innovation. Innovation activity is a set of measures and technologies to ensure the innovation process at a particular level of education, as well as this process itself. The concept of "education" in the modern world is associated with the interpretation of such terms as "training", "education", "development".

Dictionary meanings consider the term "education" as a noun from the verb "to form" in the sense of "to create", "to form" or "to develop" something new.

In a broad sense, creating new things is innovation. Thus, education at its core is already an innovation.

The innovative nature of education becomes the most important tool in its competition with other social institutions. In the current socio-economic situation, not only the content, but also the forms and technologies of education are important for creating a positive orientation of young people to education. The development of

new methods and channels of education is becoming an urgent necessity.

Innovations in education, first of all, should be aimed at creating a personality that is set up for success in any area of applying its capabilities. Accordingly, the development of innovative processes is a way to ensure the modernization of education, improving its quality, efficiency and accessibility.

Intra-subject innovations: that is, innovations implemented within the subject, which is determined by the specifics of its teaching. An example is the transition to new educational and methodological complexes and the development of author's methodological technologies.

Innovations in education are understood as the process of improving pedagogical technologies, a set of methods, techniques and means of teaching. At present, innovative pedagogical activity is one of the essential components of the educational activity of any educational institution. And this is no accident. It is

innovative activity that not only creates the basis for creating the competitiveness of an institution in the market of educational services, but also determines the directions of professional growth of a teacher, his creative search, and really contributes to the personal growth of students. Therefore, innovative activity is inextricably linked with the scientific and methodological activities of teachers and educational and research students.

The problem of the effectiveness of innovation activity that exists in modern pedagogical science is largely the result of misunderstanding, distortion of the essence of the term "innovation" itself. Innovation is a new one, designed to ensure the gradual development, improvement of the system, its transition to a qualitatively new state in the existing conditions. Innovations are carried out at the expense of the resources of the system itself and are aimed at its complete change - this is their fundamental importance. They are not limited only to the denial of the old, generally accepted, conservative, assuming the purposeful nature of innovations and their orientation to stability.

Innovations in education are implemented directly in the organization of the educational process, in programs and methods. Changes may affect teaching activities, the system of financing and evaluation of the quality of education. In modern society, education is objectively of great importance. Hence – the next stage of the search for promising areas of its development. And this is all the more relevant, since the education system currently survives mainly due to the internal margin of safety created in former times.

An innovation is an implemented innovation with high efficiency. It is the

final result of the intellectual activity of a person, his imagination, creative process, discoveries, inventions and rationalization in the form of new or different objects from the previous ones. They are characterized by the introduction to the market of completely new (improved) products (services) of human intellectual activity that have a higher scientific and technical potential, new consumer qualities, which over time, in turn, become an object for improvement. Innovative methods - methods based on the use of modern achievements of science and information technologies in education. They are aimed at improving the quality of training by developing students' creative abilities and independence (methods of problem-based and projective learning, research methods, training forms that provide for the actualization of students' creative potential and independence). Innovative methods can be implemented in both traditional and distance learning technologies.

The most effective methods in modern educational technology are: problem-based learning methods (problem presentation, heuristic and research methods), group methods (brainstorming method, situational method, group discussion, game methods), project method, modeling method, laboratory experiment, involving students in productive work during practice, etc. At the same time, the student does not receive ready-made knowledge, but obtains it; moreover, knowledge as such is not the goal of education, but becomes a means of solving the tasks set. The result of such training is not only new knowledge, but also the ability to apply it to solve problems. Active educational, cognitive and research activities of the student

contribute to the development of his personal qualities-abilities, responsibility, independence, etc. In the process of joint activity in the group, his sociability, ability to listen, ask questions, express his opinion, conduct a discussion, convince others, respect other people's opinions, and cooperate with people develop. Individual students also develop leadership skills.

Innovation processes should be implemented today in all educational structures. New types of educational institutions, management systems, new technologies and methods are manifestations of the huge potential of innovative processes. Their competent and well-thought-out implementation contributes to the deepening of positive changes in it.

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